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Ancient Indian knowledge of Environmental Awareness

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Abstract

The ancient Indian tradition has a lot of materials for the modern world. The Vedic tradition grew with the sacrificial culture simultaneously with the society. This created a history in the then society as the Vedic seers dealt with the natural phenomena. They were treated as the power house of energy in a sense that they were responsible for the altogether development of humanity. The prayers are universal in nature. They had close feelings towards nature and environment which created an atmosphere for realization of the importance of living and non-living beings. They had a strong interaction with a natural environment and hence aware of the ecological surroundings.

Keywords: Sacrifice, Nature, Culture, Environment, *Gītā*, Consciousness, awareness.

1.0 The ancient seers prayed to different Gods and Goddess and uttered various *mantras* in order to propitiate them. This tradition continued till today through sacrificial culture and daily prayers. After opening his eyes at the day break, before putting his feet on the ground, a traditional Indian chants the following verse -

समुद्रवसने देवि ! पर्वतस्तनमण्डले !

विष्णुपत्नि ! नमस्तुभ्यं पादस्पर्श क्षमस्व मे।।

(The vast ocean is your cloth, the high peaked mountains are your breast. You are the spouse of Lord Vishnu. Please forgive me because I am going to touch by my feet)

This particular stanza connected with love, respect and gratitude towards the earth, which speaks volumes about our attitude towards nature, is only a small example of our genuine concern towards the environmental awareness of a continued tradition.

In order to protect the Vedic wisdom of environment there are many text written to make others aware of the fact of spreading ecological awareness. Since a few years, there has been much hue and cry about the protection of environment. Summits are convened, seminars are held, discussions are arranged, even rallies and smaller activities are organized to create consciousness about the protection of environment. Because destruction of nature has almost incinerated the future of mankind. It is implicated that all the creatures, plants and animals

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including the mankind must be friendly to one another and use natural resources judiciously without harming to anyone.¹ There are equal rights of all the human beings on entire wealth of nature, water and food of this earth. It is the duty of every one to protect them and use them equally.

Pure water and air are the basic need of human being. It is very well advocated that water is the home of *Amṛta* and the medicines. It is our duty to realize the significance of pure water to remain healthy and cheerful.²

2.0 Centuries ago, the great seers of Indian soil had a clear understanding of this fact. They knew that men's existence was inseparably interwoven in the fabric of nature. The ravage of nature therefore would certainly result in the revenge of mankind. It was only through a cordial co-operation and co-existence with nature, they understood, that man could reach the heights of civilization not by savagely destroying it. One cannot ignore the ancient wisdom of environment. The *Gītā* testified this valuable truth in a nice couple of allegorical Verse

सहयज्ञाः प्रजाः सृष्ट्वा पुरोवाच प्रजापतिः।
अनेन प्रसविष्यध्वमेष वोऽस्त्विष्टकामधुक्।।
देवान् भावयतानेन ते देवा भावयन्तु वः।
परस्परं भावयन्तः श्रेयः परमवाप्स्यथा।।³

When the creator created man, he created *Yajña* along with it and said, "You (men) serve the gods by *yajña* and let the gods favor you (by timely rain etc.)

The intrinsic meaning of these verses is extremely illuminating. The gods are none other than the natural phenomena like air (*Vāyudeva*) fire (*Agnideva*) water (*Varuṇadeva*) etc. The pious duty of man, according to *Gītā* is to serve these gods by performing *Yajñas*. If we safe the energy, they will protect us.

Yajñas stand for these left selfless activities, performed only as a duty in order to benefit the world. *Yajñas* do not give any direct return to the performer. But benefit ultimately comes to him through the betterment of the World. *Manusmṛti* (3.70) enumerates the main *Yajñas* as- *BrahmaYajña* (ब्रह्मयज्ञ), *PitrYajñas* (पितृयज्ञ), *DaivaYajña* (दैवयज्ञ), *BhūtaYajña* (भूतयज्ञ) and *NṛYajña* (नृयज्ञ).

Teaching the students in order to transmit the vast store of knowledge to the next generation, is the *Brahma Yajña*, Performing *Srāddha* etc. (In order to remember and show one's gratitude towards the ancestors) is *PitrYajña*. Offering oblation in the sacrificial fire (mainly to purify the air and keep the atmosphere pollution free) is *Daivayajña*. Offering food etc. to the animals is

Bhutayajña. Providing food and shelter to a fellow human being (the guest) at the time of need is *Nṛyajña*. Further *Gītā* establishes a holy cycle between man and gods (nature) in the following way

Living beings survive on food. Food is produced by rain and rain is produced by the good actions of man (by the preservation of nature). He, who does not understand this cycle between man and nature, *Gītā* affirms, is a sinner and his life is futile -

एवं प्रवर्तितं चक्रं नानुवर्तयतीह यः।

अघायुरिन्द्रियारामो मोघं पार्थ ! स जीवति।।⁴

The *Gītā* further warns the mankind that every action of man has to be a *yajña* or else his actions will breed sorrows for him -

यज्ञार्थात् कर्मणोऽन्यत्र लोकोऽयं कर्मबन्धनः।।⁵

The *Gītā* further declares that this World is not meant for a non-performer of *Yajña* (a person who does not work for the World but lives selfishly for his own interest)

नायं लोकोऽस्त्ययज्ञस्य।⁶

Thus man has to co-exist and co-operate with the gods (the natural forces) or else he is destined to perish. The ancient Indian civilization, therefore, was one that doted upon Nature. Love, respect, gratitude and care for Nature flooded the life of man.

3.0 Thus, in Indian culture, there exists a strong emotional bondage with the Nature. Nature has been so endearing that man has discovered all his fondest ones in the facts of it. Earth has been invariably revered as a mother. Sky has often commanded respect of a father - द्यौर्मे पिता पृथ्वी मे माता, द्यौर्मे पिता जनिता, सा नो भूमिर्विसृजतां माता पुत्राय मे पयः।

Rivers and mountains have been bestowed with the respect of gods and goddesses. Many rigmaroles and mythologies have evolved round the impersonated rivers and mountains like Ganga, Yamuna, Himalaya and Vindhya. River banks and mountain- peaks have been famous pilgrimages. The water of great rivers have been considered so holy that an immersion in a famous river like Ganga has been regarded as one of the holiest achievements of one's life time.

One of the appellations of Lord Śiva is *Aṣṭamūrti* (he who has eight forms). The eight forms are- the earth, the water, the air, the light, the sun, the moon and man (a performer of sacrifice) -

पृथिवी सलिलं तेजो वायुराकाशमेव च।

सूर्यचन्द्रमसौ सोमयाजी चेत्यष्टमूर्तयः।।

The Vedanta upgrades the Nature to the highest pinnacle and declares that everything is Brahman. Nothing is less than Brahman.

सर्वं खलु इदं ब्रह्म

4.0 In Indian culture, plants and animals have shared a large portion of man's attention. Cow is respected as mother. Other animals like Lion, Elephant, Bull etc. and birds like peacock and swan etc. even reptiles like snake etc. have been conferred with divinity because of their mythological association with the deities.

The Sanskrit literature describes and depict emotional relations between man and nature. A few examples would not be out of place to quote -

अतन्द्रिता सा स्वयमेव वृक्षकान् घटस्तनप्रस्रवणैर्व्यवर्धयत्।

गुह्येऽपि येषां प्रथमासजन्मनां न पुत्रवात्सल्यमपाकरिष्यति॥⁷

It is described how during her penance, Pārvaṭī had planted several saplings in the precinct of her hermitage and cared them as a mother. When she actually became a mother, this kind of relation did not happen. On the contrary, these trees were always treated as elder to Kārtikeya. It is also described how a Devadāru tree, described as a son by Siva and Pārvaṭī was once damaged by a wild tusker. Viewing the plight of the tree Pārvaṭī cried bitterly as if her son Kārtikeya was injured in some battle with the demons. Moved by Pārvaṭī's feeling, Lord Siva immediately employed a lion to guard the tree day and night.

There is description how Śakuntalā could never pluck a flower, a leaf from the trees to decorate her personally (although she loved decorating herself), as she was fond of the trees like her brothers and sisters -

नादत्ते प्रियमण्डनापि भवतां स्नेहेन या पल्लवम्॥⁸

While going to her husband palace, she could not leave the hermitage without passionately embracing the tendril, her creeper sister. She could not control her tears when the deer she had nurtured with motherly affections pulled her cloth from behind in order to debar her from leaving the hermitage.

There is a description that the hermits treated animals tenderly and affectionately. There is description how animals like deer had free access to the precincts of hermitages. They were at liberty to eat the wild paddy, collected by the hermits. Hermits used to put handful of paddy inside the holes of tree trunks for the consumption of the parrots living inside.

There are also descriptions of Nature's reciprocation to the affectionate behavior of men. It is described how child Bharata used to wrest lion cubs from the lap of their mother and the lioness never harmed the playful Bharata.

It is mentioned how the plant-gods presented clothes and ornaments to Śakuntalā for her bridal make-up. There are descriptions how deer stopped eating, peacocks stopped dancing and cuckoos stopped singing when Śakuntalā was leaving the hermitage.

Conclusion

In the Sanskrit literature our ancestors described their love towards Nature. They had a peaceful co-existence with the Nature with genuine affection and concern. They were very much active in protecting the environment. But the society was never selfish. On the contrary, there was a strong emotional urge to protect the environment almost with a similar vehemence as a man protects his family members without expecting any return.

It is time, therefore to, recall our own culture, revive our own tradition, read our own literature, adopt our own way of environmental consciousness, which we have forgotten long back. Adopting the Indian way of cordial coexistence with Nature is the only way of survival, not only for India but also for the whole World from the ensuring destruction that the World is heading towards. The present catastrophe of infections and diseases through various virus can be controlled and eradicated through the ancient way of environmental awareness and protection. Hence, we need to study and interpret the śāstras accordingly, in order to protect this entire universe from hazards.

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